

ALL-Ready – The European Agroecology
Living Lab and Research Infrastructure Network: preparation phase

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Reports of ALL-Ready Pilot Co- Creation Experiences – Report n.1

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List of abbreviations

AE	Agroecology
LL	Living Lab
RI	Research Infrastructure
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
WP	Work Package
LCA	(Environmental) Life Cycle Assessment
SLCA	Social Life Cycle Analysis
EA	Economic Assessment
CA	Conservation Agriculture
AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
CSA	Coordination And Support Action
EC	European Commission
ACS	Agricultural Climate Solutions
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
GHG	Green House Gases
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
AMU	Antimicrobial Use
AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise

Abbreviations of Pilot Network Members

ISF	Institute for Sustainable Food
IF	Innovative Farmers
Lifewatch-ERIC	Lifewatch
Organic RDD	Organic Research Development and Demonstration Program
CROPSYS	CROPSYS
ÖMKi	ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab
LLAEBIO	Living Lab on Agro-Ecology and Organic Agriculture in Flanders
ZAPVS	LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre
Occitanum	Occitanum
AAFC	Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada
PA4ALL	Precision Agriculture for All
ROADMAP	ROADMAP

REWET	Wetland observatories for rewetting of drained peatlands
CarbonFarm	CarbonFarm
OasYs	OasYs
CBIO	Centre for Circular Bioeconomy Production and Management of Agricultural Biomass
Guadalinfo	Guadalinfo Living Lab

Introduction

ALL-Ready is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded by the European Commission (EC) with the aim of preparing a framework for a future European network of Living Labs (LL) and Research Infrastructures (RI) that will enable the transition towards agroecology throughout Europe. Based on the premise that agroecology can strengthen the sustainability and resilience of farming systems, the project will contribute to addressing the multiple challenges that they are facing today, including climate change, loss of biodiversity, dwindling resources, and the degradation of soil and water quality.

The future European network of Living Labs and Research Infrastructures will promote transdisciplinary, highly participatory, inclusive, and coordinated experimentation in real life settings, ensure knowledge exchange at the EU level, and the delivery of series of long-term data on ecological processes applied to agriculture in diverse conditions across the EU. It will support farmers – at farm, landscape, and regional level - in understanding and implementing agroecological practices at the scale needed for significant positive economic, environmental and social impact.

This deliverable details the co-creation experiences of the ALL-Ready pilot network taking place in WP3. WP3 – besides coordinating stakeholder engagement activities - aims to build and run a small-scale pilot network in order to test the approaches, tools and recommendations developed across the project for the implementation of the future European network.

This document contains the following: first, the rationale, objectives, selection process, and general characteristics of the pilot network. It also gives a detailed presentation of all 15 pilot members using the framework for agroecology transition developed in WP1 (Chapter 1). Second, it shows the co-creation processes in which the pilot network participates and analyses the methods and experiences of the first pilot network meeting, which was the first step in all co-creation processes planned with the pilot members (Chapter 2). Third, it also provides a summary of next steps in light of the results of current co-creation experiences, on order to prepare for upcoming activities with the pilot network (Chapter 3).

This deliverable is a living document. It will be updated each year, until the end of the project. The 2nd version will be complemented with the pilot experiences that have occurred until the second pilot network meeting and the 3rd version will collect and integrate all experiences of the pilot network until the end of the project.

1. The ALL-READY Pilot Network

1.1 Piloting the European Network of Agroecological LLs and RIs

The European Commission aims to launch a partnership (new co-funded instrument) entitled “Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures” under the Horizon Europe research and innovation framework in 2023 ([EC AE Partnership](#)). One of the aims of the partnership is to build and organise a European network of new and existing living labs and research infrastructures for knowledge sharing and co-creation on agroecology innovations at various scales across Europe. It will identify relevant existing LLs and RIs and animate the network to set the stage for a European-wide community accelerating agroecological transition. The network will develop tools for the sharing of best practices and a platform for knowledge exchange among the members, will promote the creation of new agroecology living labs and research infrastructure while ensuring cooperation within and outside the network (SCAR-AE 2021).

The ALL-Ready project contributes significantly to the creation of this future network through the development of its vision, mission, and framework for agroecology transition in Living Labs (LLs) and Research infrastructures (RIs) and through piloting a small-scale network of already existing LLs and RIs. This vision is “to accelerate the transition to agroecology throughout Europe by connecting and empowering place-based innovation from 2023 onwards through connecting agroecological LL/RIs and other open innovation initiatives across Europe that support practices for agriculture production that pilot, create and use diversity” (Mambrini-Doudet *at al.* 2022). The pilot network allows real-life experimentation on the structuring and functioning of the future European network based on co-creative and participatory methods, and the lessons learnt can directly inform the setting up of the future network.

As the members in the ALL-Ready pilot network are agroecological living labs and research infrastructures, it is important to clarify the definitions used in this deliverable.

Living Labs (LLs) are open innovation ecosystems in real-life environments, which use iterative feedback processes throughout the lifecycle of an innovation. They operate as orchestrators among citizens, research organizations, companies, and government agencies. They focus on joint value co-creation, rapid prototyping, testing, and scaling-up innovations ([ENOLL](#)). The three basic operational principles supporting LL activities are i) co-creation, ii) user-centeredness, iii) real life conditions. More specifically, agroecological living labs can be identified as initiatives that comply with the following set of criteria: i) co-creation of knowledge and innovation; ii) promotion of resilience, sustainability and diversity; iii) support for climate change adaptation and mitigation, iv) synergies between ecosystem functions; v) promotion of efficiency and responsibility in the use of natural resources; vi) development of circular and solidarity economies, value given to social and ecological justice. (Mambrini-Doudet *at al.* 2021).

Research Infrastructures (RIs) are open research facilities for experimentation at different scales (plot, farm, landscape level and networks). They are expected to contribute to bringing a corpus of knowledge for agroecology transition and are expected to have a central role in education, in providing data to stakeholders, and in providing services in an open science vision (Mambrini-Doudet *at al.* 2021).

A key assumption behind ALL-Ready is that RIs and LLs are instruments that have significant potential to contribute to amplifying the transition to agroecology in Europe.

1.1.1 Examples of existing networks

There are already networks in place, namely the Agriculture and Agri-food Working Group of the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL) and the living lab network in the frame of the

Agricultural Climate Solutions ([ACS](#)) program financed by the Agriculture and Agri-Food Canada (AAFC), which serve as good examples for the pilot network and for the development of the future European Network of Agroecological LLs and RIs. However, these are also some substantial differences.

The Canadian Government-supported ACS was launched in 2018 as a nationwide network of agroecosystem living labs to foster the development and adoption of sustainable practices and technologies by Canadian farmers, to accelerate the response to climate change and other agri-environmental challenges – but without prominent support for research infrastructures.

On the other hand, ENoLL is an international non-profit association which aims to promote and enhance the Living Lab concept globally, by facilitating knowledge exchange, joint actions, and project partnerships among members. They operate several thematic working groups, one of which is the Agriculture and Agri-food Working Group consisting of agricultural living labs from around the world. The focus of the working group and ENoLL lacks the research infrastructure component, although some of the living labs in the network identify as RIs as well. Moreover, many agricultural living labs within the ENoLL network do not operate in the agroecology domain, but rather study and contribute to conventional practices.

1.2 ALL-READY Pilot Network Objectives, Member Selection Process and Set-Up

1.2.1 Objectives

The pilot network has a triple objective:

- to act as a small-scale testbed to experiment, and to give feedback on the tools and recommendations developed in the ALL-Ready project (across WPs)
- to build strong links and cooperation between the different agroecology-focused living labs, research infrastructures and open innovation arrangements across Europe
- to co-create and realise joint network activities in line with the common agroecological interests of the pilot members.

1.2.2 Member selection

Between May and June 2021, a selection survey was launched to identify forerunner agroecological LL/RIs from the 13 partner countries. The survey was structured to gather general information and defining characteristics of the applicants in relation to specific agroecology LL/RI elements. In addition, the survey mapped individual needs and expectations from the pilot network.

The selection process took place between July-September 2021 following general network-level and individual selection criteria. The general criteria were designed to obtain an even distribution of geographical representation, scale of users, maturity level, scope of activities and agroecology scale for the whole pilot network. The individual criteria have been distinguished on LL and RI level, assuring that initiatives comply with the features of an agroecology LL or RI. Selected LLs had to fulfil five of the following criteria:

- fully describe their agroecological practice and research using LL methodology
- showcase activities or research covering transdisciplinary, mainly socio-economic aspects of agroecology
- describing their users, the different types of stakeholders and how they are involved in their co-creative processes
- describing the real-life context
- describing their products, services developed
- defining the impacts of the initiative and their contribution to the agroecology transition

Selected RIs also had to fulfil five of the following criteria:

- fully describe their agroecological practice and research
- defining the impacts of the initiative and their contribution to the agroecology transition
- describing the research resources that are provided by the initiative
- describing the tools/practices that are used by the initiative
- describing their users, the different types of stakeholders and how they are involved in their co-creative processes

After the evaluation done by the consortium members, 15 initiatives were selected for the pilot network. In addition to the 15 pilot network members (ISF, IF, Lifewatch-ERIC, Organic RDD, CROPSYS, ÖMKi, LLAEBIO, ZAPVS, Occitanum, PA4ALL, ROADMAP, REWET, CarbonFarm, OasYs, CBIO) two external advisor organisations (AAFC and Guadalinfo) have been added, to support the network. The members are very different in size and objective. Some of them are certified living labs by ENoLL, but the majority are open innovation structures in the form of national, territorial networks, LL-like projects, or experimental sites. In **Appendix 1**, all 15 pilot members are presented in detail based on the four key features of agroecological living labs and research infrastructures (context, aim, activities, participants) in the framework for agroecology transition elaborated by WP1. Each member presentation also contains additional features on the achievements and methods used in the initiatives.

Preparations for the network set-up were organised between October and November 2021, while the first pilot meeting took place online in December 2021. In order to remain open and inclusive, a new application period with a similar selection survey will be launched in June 2022. Therefore, the number of members and composition of the pilot network will be subject to change.

1.3 Characteristics and Activities of the Pilot Network

1.3.1 Characteristics

The pilot network consists of 15 initiatives of which eight identify as AE LL, seven as AE RI. From the advisors, Guadalinfo is a living lab while ACS identifies as both a LL and RI:

Living Labs:

Belgium - LLAEBIO (Living Lab on Agro-Ecology and Organic Agriculture in Flanders)
 Hungary – ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab
 Serbia – PA4ALL (Precision Agriculture for All)
 Denmark –, ROADMAP, CarbonFarm
 France – Occitanum
 UK - Innovative Farmers

Research Infrastructures:

Spain – LifeWatch-ERIC
 Denmark – ReWet DK, CROPSYS, CBIO, Organic RDDP
 France – OasYs, LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre
 UK - Institute of Sustainable Food

Advisors:

Canada – Agricultural Climate Solutions (LL&RI)
 Spain – Guadalinfo (LL)

1.3.1.1 Geographical representation

The composition of the network is very diverse, representing all four European regions (Figure 1):

- **Northern** (CROPSYS, REWET, CBIO, Organic RDDP, CarbonFarm, ROADMAP)
- **Southern** (LifeWatch-ERIC, Occitanum)
- **Western** (ISF, LLAEBIO, OASYS, ZAPVS, Innovative Farmers)
- **Eastern Europe** (PA4ALL, ÖMKi)

Figure 1. European map of the pilot network members

1.3.1.2 Scope of activities

The members also differ in terms of the geographic scope of their activities:

- local (ZAPVS, Occitanum)
- regional (REWET, LLAEBIO)
- national (PA4ALL, ÖMKi, CROPSYS, OASYS, CBIO, IF, Organic RDD, CarbonFarm)
- international (ISF, LifeWatch-ERIC, ROADMAP)

1.3.1.3 Maturity level of the initiatives

The initiatives also represent diverse maturity levels, from very young to more experienced:

- short lifespan (<1 year) (Occitanum)
- medium lifespan (1-2 years) (LLAEBIO)
- long (mature) lifespan (2-4 years) (PA4ALL, ISF, LifeWatch-ERIC, ROADMAP, Organic RDD)
- very long (very mature) lifespan (>4 years) (ÖMKi, CROPSYS, OasYs, REWET, CBIO, ZAPVS, IF, CarbonFarm)

1.3.1.4 Scale of users in the initiatives

Network member initiatives also differ regarding the scale of users (for AE LLs, users are usually the farmers, but often stakeholders in the agri-food value chain; for AE RIs, they are researchers, as well as, occasionally, farmers, advisors, and citizens) from small to large-scale initiatives:

- small scale (< 50 users) (PA4ALL, CROPSYS, LifeWatch-ERIC, OasYs, CarbonFarm)
- medium scale (50 – 200 users) (LLAEBIO, ÖMKi, ROADMAP, Occitanum, CBIO, Organic RDD)
- large scale (> 200 users) (ISF, REWET, ZAPVS, IF)

1.3.2 Activities

The activities of the pilot network are interlinked with basically all WPs of the project and were formed to achieve the three main objectives, (1) aiming to build a community through collaborative activities, (2) providing feedback on the concepts and recommendations developed by ALL-Ready and (3) co-creating different tools and programs through designing, prototyping, testing, and evaluating during the project lifetime.

The co-creation activities taking place in the pilot network include the co-development of the structure, operations, and joint network activities in WP3, the co-design of a capacity building programme within WP5, co-construction of the sustainability of the future European network in WP4 and the building of a Virtual Lab tool in WP6. These activities consist of multiple stages and are running in parallel until the end of the project. Moreover, their participation is crucial in the yearly pilot network meetings

In addition, the pilot network is also consulted, and it gives feedback occasionally on concepts and documents developed by other WPs: the framework, criteria, vision and mission and questionnaire for agroecology transition in WP1, identification of best LL/RI initiatives across Europe in WP2 or sharing of news and updates about themselves and participating in the ALL-Ready Prize contest organised by WP7.

2. Co-creation process in the Pilot Network

2.1 Co-creation of value: scientific background

Although co-creation has now become an extremely widespread and popularised term, even a review of relevant literature does not provide a clear definition. This term is used in corporate marketing, business, and consumer-centred discourse just as frequently as in public-private partnerships, multi-stakeholder platforms, and living labs involving citizens who focus on innovation and research. Co-creation in the corporate sector describes the process of value creation through the active collaboration of the consumers, who are allowed to co-develop the product and service experience to fit their needs and context (Kambil *et al.* 1999.) This is a continuous cooperation that takes place between the firm and the consumers, supported by the consumers (Jansen and Pieters, 2017).

However, for the purpose of this deliverable, in the ALL-Ready project, the understanding developed by living labs on co-creation is more fitting. Co-creation in living labs is a living concept and refers to a form of open innovation, where the development of new value happens in cooperation between the experts and a variety of stakeholders from industry, research, public institutions, and civil society, in which the inputs of the user play a central role (Schumacher and Feurstein 2007, Hagy *et al.* 2016, Mambrini-Doudet *et al.* 2021). Also, the involvement of multiple stakeholders creates a multi-contextual scene in which the actors engage and interact with other stakeholders during every step of the co-creation process from problem definition to piloting (Ballon *et al.* 2005, Kreiling and Paunov 2021).

In the context of ALL-Ready, the focus is on agroecological living labs and research infrastructures. Mambrini-Doudet *et al.* (2021) highlights that the co-creation in agroecological living labs support the transition to agroecology, and the co-development of knowledge through the sharing of tacit and implicit knowledge. Also, including the knowledge of local communities is particularly important, as is fostering the participation of all relevant stakeholders in agroecology at local and global scales (farmers to consumer associations). This can mobilize and bring together complementary and transversal agroecological expertise which increases the speed and uptake of innovations while also increasing awareness and relevance of agroecological transition and, at the same time, addressing socio-economic challenges via the involvement of civil society. Research infrastructures are more focused on providing services and facilities mainly for the research community, but sometimes for other societal actors as well. Although co-creation is not a requirement, there are agroecological RIs that support agroecology transition through the co-design and co-development of specific Virtual Research Environments applied to agroecology research. Moreover, during systemic experiments, including the redesign of systems or long-term monitoring, other stakeholders such as farmers and advisors are becoming more and more involved, therefore creating space for similar open innovation and co-creation processes happening in living labs. (e.g., networks of farms at regional or national level, platforms where collective innovation is ongoing, and where scientists are engaged) (Mambrini-Doudet *et al.* 2021)

According to Puerari *et al.* (2018), five common elements of co-creation in living labs can be distinguished, which not only exist in themselves but often influence and relate to one another:

- 1) Purpose of co-creation: There are two possible purposes of co-creation. Either working towards a common goal or an outcome, or focusing on learning itself, with the stakeholders cooperating on knowledge creation or sharing, or to learn from one another, and to develop networks or a community. The two can run simultaneously as well.
- 2) Formal and informal co-creation:
 - a) formal: environment organised by initiators or intermediaries which is constructed around defined procedures and steps, and the participants are often selected based on criteria that makes them valuable for the co-creation process.
 - b) informal: the co-creation process emerges organically out of necessity or out of shared goals. The environment is not organised by official planning or procedures, and both the selection of participants and the rules develop over time.
- 3) Ownership: Running the co-creation process requires the definition of different roles and the provision of the right tools to the right people. Depending on who determines the roles, the intermediary or initiator often takes the dominant role and defines the direction of the co-creation process. But the intermediary can open up the process to all stakeholders to share ownership.
- 4) Motivation for co-creation: Since co-creation, like any other activity, can create a variety of costs for the stakeholders (time-consuming, monetary costs, etc.), the benefits of participation need to be clearly articulated. The motivation of the stakeholders is influenced by their goals, resources, and expectations. The motivation can be intrinsic (without any external influence, for the sake of co-creation) or extrinsic (monetary compensation, future investment, recognition, etc.)
- 5) Spaces-places of co-creation: Co-creation occurs in a place-based (often local) socio-spatial context which also helps when analysing the specific conditions in which co-creation takes place. This contributes to the wider adaptation and implementation of an innovation within a given local community.

However, each element has its own challenges that needs to be tackled during every co-creation process (Table 1).

Element	Definition	Challenge	Solution
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Either working towards a common goal or an outcome • The goal can be the learning itself, knowledge creation or sharing 	How to engage all stakeholders?	Shared goals, develop close personal relations, build trust
Formal or informal co-creation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal: environment organised by intermediaries, with defined procedures, participants are selected • Informal: the co-creation process emerges out of necessity, no official planning, no selection of participants 	How to create effective governance, operations, and structure?	Plan of actions, procedures, working groups, modes of operation
Ownership	Stakeholders have control over the steps and decision-making of the co-creation process.	How to develop a sense of ownership and use commonly created data and knowledge?	Detailed guidance, formalization of contracts
Motivation	Reasons of stakeholders for participating in the co-creation process.	How to incentivize processes and participants in the long run?	Reward system, recognition, benefit package, monitoring of participation
Spaces and places	Co-creation is bound to the place and local context in which it occurs.	How to adapt to changing environments (community, institutional, etc.)?	Flexibility, inclusive management

Table 1. Corresponding challenges and solutions of the five co-creation elements

Lastly, the co-creation experience of individual actors also helps to evaluate the overall co-creation process. This experience is defined as a personal knowledge or value creation process, which is ongoing and dependant on the degree and nature of the individual's involvement with other stakeholders (Prahalad and Ramaswamy 2004, Randall 2011). This personal experience also encompasses the individual's subjective feelings, state of mind, competency, expertise, and enjoyment resulting from the co-creation activity (Füller *et al.* 2011).

The ALL-Ready pilot members' personal experiences about the co-creation processes taking place in the pilot network will be evaluated in the 2nd and 3rd version of this deliverable.

2.2 Co-creation in the First Pilot Network Meeting

2.2.1 Co-creation processes in the pilot network

During the ALL-Ready project, the pilot network acts as a testbed to not only experiment and give feedback on the different concepts and recommendations developed, but to co-create and co-design new tools and activities for the pilot members and the larger agroecology community as well.

This co-creation process started in the first pilot network meeting, using different methods or a mixture of methods, and is being applied through three work packages: (1) WP3 - where the members co-create joint network activities, and operations, (2) WP5 – where the members co-design and implement a capacity building program and (3) WP6 – where the pilot members also co-design the Virtual Lab tool.

WP4 will co-construct the implementation and sustainability plan of the future European network of LLs and RIs with the help of the pilot network and a wide range of stakeholders starting later in the project. The current co-creation experiences from the first pilot network meeting therefore do not contain the WP4-related results, which will be detailed in the 2nd version of this deliverable.

Besides co-creation, the members are also heavily involved through consulting and informing on specific topics or concepts in WP1, WP2 and WP7, but this involvement is not detailed in this document as it does not constitute a multistage co-creative process.

a) Joint Network Activities

Figure 2. Co-creation process of the joint pilot network activities in WP3

The co-creation of joint network activities and operations is a process consisting of five main steps (Figure 2) starting from the first pilot network meeting until the end of the project in 2023. However, the resulting experiences and lessons learnt are expected to contribute to the future network. The 1st step in this process was the collection of expectations and needs of the pilot network from the members in the form of an online selection survey in June 2021. The results of the survey were validated and finally decided on during the first pilot network meeting in December 2021, where the members also mapped their collaboration potential and joint network activities as a 2nd step through workshops. The 3rd step in the process will be the finalization of the collaborative themes resulting from the mapping exercise and a co-design of an action plan and supporting operations and structure in mid-April 2022. Then comes the actual realization and monitoring of the activities by the members as a 4th step until early-mid 2023 through online and in-person meetings, workshops and surveys. Finally, the experiences and lessons learnt are evaluated by the members as 5th step at the end of the project.

b) Developing the Capacity Building Programme

Figure 3. Co-creation process of the capacity building programme in WP5

The development of the Capacity Building Programme for the future network in the frame of WP5 is also a co-creative process consisting of four main stages (Figure 3) running in parallel with the co-creation of joint network activities in WP3 from the first pilot network meeting until the end of the project in 2023. The 1st stage was the scoping exercise to identify necessary competencies and skills to run an AE LL/RI and to transition to agroecology, done in a workshop in the first pilot network meeting in December 2021, which will be fed into the design of the programme. The capacity building programme will be prototyped in the 2nd stage by the members through co-design workshops in mid-2022. Then the programme will be tested and evaluated in the 3rd stage through on-site workshops in some member LL/RIs during late 2022, and early 2023. Finally, the programme will be implemented with the help of the members in the form of three capacity-building trainings until the end of the project.

c) Co-designing the Virtual Lab

The co-design of the Virtual Lab - an online tool to make it easier for members to find and securely access agroecology LL/RI related data and use it in innovative ways – is also a simultaneously running process consisting of six steps (Figure 4) with the two previously mentioned co-creation courses. The 1st step was the identification of pilot member needs in relation to the Virtual Lab through a workshop during the first pilot network meeting in December 2021. The 2nd step will be the co-creation of value and features for the Lab with the members in early 2022. Then the Virtual Lab will be prototyped and tested by the members as a 3rd step and evaluated in the 4th step during late 2022 through a series of workshops. As a 5th step, the initial prototype will be further improved based on the evaluation and finalized in early 2023. Finally, the tool will be implemented via two training workshops with the members by the end of the project.

Figure 4. Co-creation process of the Virtual Lab tool in WP6

To start the three co-creation processes, three distinct workshops were organised during the pilot network meeting in an online form. The workshops were structured to launch the 1st and 2nd steps of three co-creation process.

2.2.2 Objectives and organization of Pilot Network Meeting

The first pilot network meeting was organised by ÖMKi on 13-14th December 2021 with support from WP1 (INRAE), WP3 (ILVO, Ecologic), WP4 (Thünen Institute, BioSense Institute), WP5 (ENoLL) and WP6 (LifeWatch-ERIC) partners. The meeting agenda and the list of participants are detailed in **Appendix 2 and 3**.

The meeting was a combination of presentations and active workshop sessions. Three types of presentation sessions were organised: a) introductory presentations about ALL-Ready, the aims of the pilot network and the European Agroecology Partnership; b) presentations of 17 pilot members and c) Work Package (WP) presentations addressing each WP.

Besides presentations, the meeting included three different workshop sessions, each organised and facilitated by the above-mentioned WPs.

The overall objective of the meeting was to launch the ALL-Ready pilot network which has been in preparation since July 2021. To reach this aim, specific objectives were also pursued:

- (1) to familiarise members with the project through introductory presentations about ALL-Ready, the aims of the pilot network and the European Partnership “**Accelerating farming systems transition: agroecology living labs and research infrastructures**”,
- (2) to allow the members to get to know each other and initiate cooperation through the pilot member presentations and the match-making workshop,
- (3) to present and ask feedback from the members on already developed concepts of the project such as the inclusion criteria, vision and mission for the future network or the use of the online selection tool and
- (4) to contribute to the ongoing work of different WPs with members’ expertise through the five workshops.

The three workshops – each with specific goals - were structured to contribute to achieving the above-mentioned objectives.

2.2.3 Co-creation methods applied during the Pilot Network Meeting

Three different methods were applied during the three online workshops designed to differently engage the members to reach the desired goals which are summarised in Table 2.

The following methods were used:

1. Validation session: this method invited participants to work on and discuss a predefined set of topics and ideas to spark debate and arrive at a common understanding or set of preferences.

This method was applied only during the joint network activities workshop. In the case of the pilot network, the predefined set of ideas were presented in relation to the expectations and needs of the pilot network, individual agroecological interests and activities and the framework for agroecological transition.

2. Mapping: this method involved collecting information verbally or in written form from participants on a given area of interest, and then recording it on an online workboard or some type of ‘map’ that the group can logically and visually follow and constantly give feedback. This was the primary method that was used by all three workshops.
3. Match-making: this method helped to identify and connect (match) members, initiatives (LL/RIs) with common agroecological interests, activities, expertise, experiences and/or strengths, which has created collaborative connections, themes, linkages and realising opportunities that mutually benefit both parties. This method was applied only during the joint network activities workshop.

Table 2. The goals and methods used in the three workshops of the first pilot network meeting

	Goal	Method
Joint activities for the pilot network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to validate the inputs given by the members during the pilot member selection process (May-June 2021) about their individual expectations and needs from the pilot network and individual agroecological interests 	Online workshop: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • two validation sessions • mapping in two groups

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to allow members to get to know each other's LL/RIs activities better while mapping the cooperation potential between them based on their agroecological interests and activities to lay the groundwork for future collaboration to co-create joint activities for the pilot network 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> match-making in two groups
Exploring the added value of a future network and competencies for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to collect inputs from the members on the needed competencies to (1) foster transition to agroecology in general and (2) set up and run an agroecology living lab and/or research infrastructure 	Online workshop: mapping in two groups
Building a Virtual Lab	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> to provide an introduction about a Virtual Lab and what it is used for to launch the co-design of the Virtual Lab for Agroecology by the identification of the needs from the pilot network 	Online workshop session: mapping in two groups

2.2.4 Co-creation experiences of the Pilot Network Meeting

In the 1st version of this deliverable, the co-creation experiences of the three co-creative workshops will be assessed based on the elements of co-creation, types of members involved, format, results, feedback on the experiences, and challenges.

2.2.4.1 Elements of the three co-creation workshops

Table 3 details the analysis of the three co-creation workshops (*Co-creation of joint collaborative activities for the pilot network*, *Exploring the competencies and skills for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI* and *Building the Virtual Lab*) based on the five elements of co-creation.

Table 3. Assessment of the three co-creation workshops based on the five elements of co-creation

	Co-creation of joint collaborative activities for the pilot network	Capacity Building Programme: Exploring the competencies and skills for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI	Building the Virtual Lab
Purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Working towards the realization of joint network activities as an outcome Building a network and community of AE LLs and RIs for sharing and creating knowledge and best practices 	Preparing and testing a Capacity Building Programme to support the transition agroecology by promoting agroecology, LL, and RI approaches	Co-designing and testing the Agroecology Virtual Lab tool to find, share, store, use, access, visualize and analyse agroecology LL/RI related data to improve the knowledge about agroecology practices.
Formal/Informal	Formal: a targeted, organised environment by ALL-Ready, defined procedures, members went through selection	Formal	Formal
Ownership	After the first step of workshops, it is difficult to judge the ownership. Currently, the coordinator of the pilot network has the biggest ownership over the co-creation processes, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps will be opened up to the members just as the structuring of the network.	Currently, the coordinator of the pilot network and WP5 partners have the biggest ownership over the co-creation processes, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps will be opened up to the members.	Currently, the coordinator of the pilot network and WP6 have the biggest ownership over the co-creation processes, the steps are pre-planned, but the decision-making over these steps will be opened up to the members.
Motivation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Networking and knowledge exchange: to get to know other scientists and farmers from other LL/RIs, share experiences what other initiatives are doing – co-creation and meaningful research, knowledge exchange with other countries - explore the results they obtain (generic or not), and see whether they obtain the same results or not in a different site 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving and developing further member LL/RI practices and the skills of LL/RI stakeholders. Tailored trainings, tools, and guides for the members on how to build, run and scale-up an AE LL/RIs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connecting with other RI/LLs through data-sharing. Improving member understanding of agroecological processes. Making simulations to identify how specific scenarios, for example, climate change or management decisions can affect LL/RI activity.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discovering new agroecological practices, inspire other scientists to work on agroecological systems. • Teaming up with others based on similar goals, screening for potential collaboration: writing proposals together, applying for funds. • Building better links with policy makers. 		
Spaces/places	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online sphere, each member joining from home environments representing their own local LL/RI networks • Wider space is the environment of the pilot network itself 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online • Wider space is the environment of the pilot network itself 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online • Wider space is the environment of the pilot network itself

2.2.4.2 Types of members involved

17 coordinators of the member agroecological living labs and research infrastructures were involved in all three workshops: 13 representing research institutes, one representing farmers/farmers advisors, two non-profit non-governmental organizations, one governmental organization and one funding body.

It is important to note that the living labs and research infrastructures involved in the pilot network comprise a variety of stakeholders and users depending on their objective (see Appendix 3). However, for the purpose of the pilot network, the best type of user is the one who runs and operates the initiative, who can give an insight into the activities, stakeholders, and internal process of the initiatives.

2.2.4.3 Format

The workshops were conducted online using zoom due to the Covid-19 pandemic situation. The MURAL online platform was used for workshop tasks and exercises.

During all three co-creation workshops, the members were grouped into two breakout groups which helped to dive deeper into specific questions and topics.

2.2.4.4 Results

Co-creation of joint collaborative activities workshop

a) Expectations and needs of the pilot network

The very first step to begin the co-creation of collaborative activities for the pilot network was the finalization of pilot network expectations and needs. This process started with the pilot member selection in July 2021, when the members individually submitted their expectations and needs in writing. The validation exercise therefore built on these submitted expectations and needs which were reviewed and further refined by the members. Then, they created and decided on a ranking list of expectations and needs:

Expectations (in order of importance):

1. Knowledge exchange/ knowledge sharing/co-creation between LLs and RIs: Sharing challenges, best practices of living lab models, getting to know/more effectively implementing the co-creation process and data sharing among LLs or RIs seemed important.
2. Future collaboration in international research projects on agroecology: To create a platform for members to find each other with the goal of potentially applying for funding together
3. Training the members in (1) new methodologies and approaches for agroecological transition and (2) how to share agroecological expertise with regions and countries which are not yet engaged
4. Networking: To link up with other organisations with similar goals and profiles across Europe to pool resources and to extend members' network
5. Testing and experimenting the tools and knowledge developed during ALL-Ready: having capacity building and training on becoming LLs/RIs
6. Ensuring an active role for the members in the future Partnership: by honing members' skills in relation to agroecology transition or on how to run/develop AE RIs/LLs.
7. Discovering new agroecological practices

8. Developing co-creatively common activities and to set agroecology research topics/priorities for the network: by also choosing the trending topics for agroecology transitions

Needs (in order of importance):

1. Creating and maintaining an enabling environment for the pilot to exchange experiences and best practices: including sharing of information on coming conferences, relevant events, creation of bibliography database
2. Ensuring access to stakeholders across the EU (farmers, agri-tech companies, and policy makers) through the pilot network
3. Keeping the interest and trust ongoing between the members and ensuring the future involvement of the members in the future partnership by strengthening international collaboration to build capacity
4. Empowering members to adapt transdisciplinarity in their LL/RI activities
5. Building confidence and trust among the pilot members during the project
6. Having a common agenda of agroecology research priorities with an LL and RI approach
7. Looking at the possibility to replicate member AE LL/RI results/methods in other pedoclimatic and socio-economic contexts
8. Evaluating activities linked to the co-creation process

Figure 5. Mural validation exercise on the expectations of the pilot network

b) Mapping the collaboration potential and joint network activities

This workshop comprised three main steps, building upon one another using validation, mapping and match-making methods as presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Three steps and corresponding methods used in joint network activities workshop

STEP 1: Exploration of agroecological LL/RI interests and topics

12 agroecological topics were given in advance on Mural based on the inputs and information from the selection process. Members had to choose the agroecological topics that best correspond to their activities in living labs and research infrastructures. In addition, they had the opportunity to note down other topics of interest.

Altogether, 21 topics emerged, out of which **sustainable soil management, sustainable cropping/animal systems and digitization in agroecology** were the most addressed ones among the member LL/RIs. There were a few topics that were only limited to the scope of some members like rotational grazing, antimicrobial resistance, or non-food/feed supply chains.

Table 4 summarises the most common agroecological topics and the members engaged in these topics. However, challenges that individually affect members were separately listed in **Appendix 4**.

Table 4. Common and individual agroecological interests of the members

Agroecological LL/RI interests	Engaged Members
Sustainable soil management, soil carbon sequestration (regenerative agriculture)	CROPSYS, CarbonFarm, LLAEBIO, ÖMKi, Innovative Farmers, AAFC, ZAPVS, OasYs, ISF
Sustainable arable cropping practices	CROPSYS, CarbonFarm, LLAEBIO, ÖMKi, Innovative Farmers, AAFC, ZAPVS, OasYs, Occitanum, Organic RDD
Digitization in agroecology, application of ICT tools for knowledge sharing among farmers	Occitanum, Guadalinfo, LifeWatch, Innovative Farmers, AAFC, ISF
Chemical pesticide-free plant protection	Carbonfarm, ÖMKi, ZAPVS, OasYs, Innovative Farmers
Agroforestry	Innovative Farmers, CarbonFarm, OasYs, LLAEBIO, Organic RDD

Agroecological market development	ÖMKi, Guadalinfo, ROADMAP, Innovative Farmers
Short and resilient food supply chains	ÖMKi, Innovative Farmers, ZAPVS
Mixed crop-dairy system and animal welfare, animal nutrition	Innovative Farmers, OasYs, ROADMAP
Food nutrition and health	Guadalinfo, ROADMAP, Innovative Farmers
Sustainable water use and management	Occitanum, OasYs, Innovative Farmers
Organic farming	LLAEBIO, ÖMKi, Organic RDD
Moving from practice-based thinking to systems thinking for agroecology	LLAEBIO, OasYs, AAFC, ÖMKi
Landscape management	ZAPVS, LifeWatch
Sustainable management of genetic resources	ÖMKi, Innovative Farmers
Making new crops acceptable by farmers and consumers (e.g., soybean, grains, legumes)	CROPSYS, Innovative Farmers
Using renewable resources in agroecology practice	Occitanum, Innovative Farmers
Culturally appropriate crops (especially with indigenous communities)	Innovative Farmers, AAFC

STEP 2: Mapping the collaboration potential between the members

Building on the previous exercise, this time the members had to list the most prominent agroecology-related research activities and challenges in relation to the previously noted agroecological interests. They also had to highlight which of their activities they like to put forth for future collaboration, then make matches with other members' activities where they see cooperation potential.

The aim was to achieve a better understanding among the members about each other's LL/RI activities while mapping the cooperation potential among them to prepare for future collaborative activities.

Each member had a card on Mural containing individual information about their respective LL/RIs (type of the initiative, agroecological interest, activities, challenges, and future research topics):

Figure 7. Sample member card from Mural (Innovative Farmers)

Table 5 summarises the challenges that are common among some members, with **funding of LL/RI activities, improving end-user and stakeholder engagement** and **data management** being the most prevalent challenges.

Table 5. Common challenges of the pilot members

Common Challenges	Affected Members
Tightening the links between the stakeholders with the initiative (stakeholder engagement researcher motivation, sharing knowledge); encourage end-users (primarily farmers and smaller companies) to take part, to define activities	Organic RDD, LLAEBIO, CROPSYS, ROADMAP, ZAPVS, Innovative Farmers, Occitanum, Guadalinfo
Funding of the LL/RI activities; how to fund farmers for their expertise and on-farm experiments	LLAEBIO, ZAPVS, CROPSYS, Innovative Farmers, ÖMKi
Managing data within LL/RIs and lack of data sharing and use of data platforms	Occitanum, ZAPVS, AAFC, ÖMKi, LifeWatch
LLs is new to researchers, not really known in agriculture and among stakeholders – addressing the reluctance to cooperate	Organic RDD, ÖMKi, AAFC, Guadalinfo, Innovative Farmers
Maintaining/improving management practices (in relation to intercropping, weed management, soil quality) and outputs (yields)	Carbonfarm, OASYS

Moving from practice-based thinking to system thinking	AAFC, Organic RDD, LLAEBIO
Documenting and measuring (climate) effects of treatments, practices	Carbonfarm, AAFC

The definition of challenges, whether common or individual, reflect the problems that member LL/RIs face in their everyday operations. In order to meet the expectations of the pilot network, the network can act as a medium to address some of these challenges through collaborative activities (match-making). However, members emphasised the need to further refine and find solutions to tackle the challenges listed in Table 5.

As results of the match-making exercise, five main collaborative themes emerged each having specific activities: (1) collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments, (2) collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing, (3) collaboration in long-term monitoring of agroecosystems, (4) advice for evidence-based agricultural policy development and (5) facilitation of EU project proposal development.

Figure 8 depicts the five collaborative themes and their connection to the common challenges. It is important to note the connections depicted need further exploration and validation by the members in future co-creation workshops.

Figure 8. Five main collaborative themes of the pilot members linked to common challenges

Appendix 5 details the specific activities with collaborators within the five collaborative themes.

During the match-making exercise, members, in addition to the challenges and current activities, highlighted new LL/RI activities that they are currently not engaged in, but would like to deal with in the future. The list of these future activities are presented in **Appendix 6**.

STEP 3: Joint network activities

After individual match-making, using mapping methodology, members further explored joint network activities that they would like to see implemented on the whole network level which will support the collaborative activities in the duration of the ALL-Ready project. Four main supportive joint network activities emerged which are listed below:

1. Creating and maintaining a platform (online) for members for sharing knowledge and methods for participatory approaches and information:
 - Building a library of best practices/examples/tools for knowledge sharing (esp. with farmers outside of the LLs) and for co-creation
 - Creating a contact network of scientists/researchers interested to work on agroecology on various pedoclimatic and agronomic contexts
 - Sharing relevant events about AE LL/RIs
 - Organising regular updates (email) on Horizon Europe calls and consortium construction
 - Developing common capacity-building materials

2. Measuring and evaluating the impact of the pilot members' activities, research:
 - Developing a strategy to design the minimum indicators for assessing AE transition that will help the LL and RI governance and accounting for local specificities
 - Developing indicators or methods to assess resilience in pilot members' agroecological systems

3. Forming thematic working groups within the pilot network based on the collaborative themes

4. Organising workshops (co-design with members) to discuss very practical challenges:
 - GDPR/Data Management - how to best implement sharing of data coming out of living labs which could be useful for other databases/knowledge hubs
 - Best practice around facilitating useful conversations between groups of farmers and other stakeholders on innovation needs & ideas
 - Maintaining of living labs - how to avoid farmer dropout, learning workshops on common challenges when running a LL
 - Product development
 - Dealing with staffing changes in living labs (e.g., researchers/facilitators) - how to manage that transition & maintain group cohesion (between farmers and stakeholders, researchers, facilitators, etc)

Figure 9. Joint network activity exercise from Mural

Capacity Building Program: Exploring the competencies and skills for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI

a) Main competencies for AE transition

Competencies for running an Agroecology LL or RI

During this exercise, the members focused particularly on skills unique for a coordinator of an AE LL/RI. For some, the skills necessary to facilitate an AE LL or an AE RI do not differ from the skills to facilitate any other RI or LL.

Six main competency categories for agroecology transition emerged from the inputs:

1. Leadership & agility competencies:

- watch over the mission and vision of the LL/RI and managing conflicting demands from the outside (the achievement of the goals defined together, bridge small daily actions to the overall goal of agroecology transition, not be overwhelmed by contradictory demands)
- encourage others to get things done
- encourage people to join the LL (e.g., how to get some people on board of the LL, very specifically policy makers and social scientists)
- delineation of responsibilities
- decision-making

2. Organizational competencies

- planning and time management
- documentation skills
- ability to change plans

3. Networking competencies and actor knowledge

- ability to build relationships
 - listening skills
 - knowing your stakeholders (understanding others strengthens participant involvement)
 - important to include social scientists to recognise opportunities to make or take roles in the LL
 - communication skills
4. Facilitating competencies:
- internal conflict management especially regarding different views on agroecology of different members in the living labs
 - active listening
 - forward thinking and ability to make synthesis
 - identify key challenges and opportunities
 - be able to bridge between different actors from various backgrounds and thus different ways of thinking
 - understand co-design methods
 - facilitate user-drive process
 - make a shared goal
 - methodological skills
 - in-depth knowledge about processes
5. Personal skills: encouraging others, people skills; acting as a team player; positive and constructive mindset
6. Systems thinking: to be able to think across disciplines (natural vs. social sciences) and have a systemic approach.

Specific knowledge of both research and practical farming skills of the sectors. The coordinator needs to have a very good overview of agroecology and what it is about.

Important competencies for actors in AE LL and/or RI

Specific competencies were mentioned only for two groups of actors:

For farmers, it is important to develop the skill of “public speaking” (e.g., when they are interviewed). Furthermore, curiosity and patience are important in agroecology transition.

For researchers, the ability and willingness to conduct good research in an environment of change and innovation is important. They should understand ‘how to set up experiments in real-life context’.

More competencies were added, but not specified for a certain actor in the LL/RI:

- Communication and networking skills: collaboration and active listening
- Personal skills: openness, holding back solutions before defining problems, team player, flexibility, willingness to allocate time for longer period
- Engagement for the network
- Systems thinking
- AE principles and practical AE knowledge
- Technical experience
- Digital competencies
- Knowledge of innovation management
- Knowledge of risk management
- Social sciences

Pilot members also summed up the competencies that are well developed in their LLs or RIs. These member specific competencies are listed in **Appendix 7**.

b) Competencies to be developed in the LL/RI

To focus the capacity building program on competencies that AE LL and RI want to develop or further upgrade, the members were asked to identify their actual needs for competencies that need to be developed for their initiative. These needs are listed below:

- **Business and marketing skills** can be achieved through involving an external expert for this role or by developing this skill internally.

- **Social and economic sciences**

Better understanding of socio-economic aspects like food sovereignty, farmers' income, or difficulties of access to lands needs to be applied in LL/RIs which are majorly organised from the perspective of natural scientists who don't know anything about the complex reality farmers have to deal with. Also, recognising the importance of human/social dimensions of innovation and adoption is just as important.

- **Data management**
- **Ability to diversify funding options**
- **Systems thinking**

Systems thinking is needed for dealing with complexity. Systems thinking is needed to approach agroecology not as a set of single practices but as a systems approach. For example, farmers mention that they do not adopt practices but work in a farming system. Researchers are sometimes very much focused on a particular topic/practice or scientific discipline but do not see how this might benefit or fit agroecology transition as a systems approach.

- **Design thinking** can help people to deal with the various knowledge (e.g., scale, sub-systems, etc.).
- **Facilitation skills and co-creation methods**

Development of skills and knowledge on how to set up experiments together in an atmosphere of confidence or how to start and set up a LL. Some challenges were mentioned that might hamper good collaboration in a co-creation setting. One challenge is to set up new collaborations to integrate additional expertise within the LL (e.g., including people as facilitating interaction between research and practice, including other scientific disciplines in the LL among which political sciences, social sciences, etc.). Further challenges are how to stimulate interaction between these different stakeholders and how to communicate with all different stakeholders (e.g., policy makers).

- **More ecological knowledge** and background for different kind of stakeholders, especially the farmers and policy makers if we want to move agroecology forward.
- **Skills/methods for monitoring/measuring carbon sequestration and GHG emissions**

Figure 10. Mural exercise on competencies for transition to agroecology and for running LL/RI

The last part of the workshop investigated which role a network of living labs and research infrastructures can play in relation to building capacities. The roles highlighted by the members are detailed in **Appendix 8**.

Building the Virtual Lab

The following results emerged from the Virtual Lab co-creation workshop:

a) Needs of the pilot network that can be covered by a Virtual Lab

1. Sharing knowledge, data, and results (quantitative and qualitative) on specific agroecological practices and best practices.
2. Sharing information on other Living Labs.
3. Saving data, research papers, information, and other types of files.
4. A place to collaborate as a network.
5. Others: Attracting scientists, sharing tools, knowledge sharing on competencies relevant for agroecology, linking experts with topics, including the 7S framework of ICT (Strategy, Structure, Systems, Shared Values, Skills, Style, and Staff), links with other databases through easy pipelines.

b) Expected outputs of the Virtual Lab:

1. Geographical overview of the network and the main characteristics of the LL/RIs.
2. Overview on good agroecological practices and living labs/research infrastructures (e.g., a library of resources).
3. A dynamic and user-friendly platform for network members.
4. A searchable data platform.
5. A place to announce learning sessions.
6. Others:
 - A space to raise awareness of the data produced in research infrastructures.
 - A prototype that can be developed further by the Agroecology Partnership.
 - Comprehensive data and knowledge space for future collaboration among living labs and research infrastructures.
 - A space that will bring together the entire network.
 - Communication and networking tools (e.g., chat function) should be used to ensure participation.
 - Guides on trial design for farmer-led/farmer-centric trials.
 - Media/videos about specific practices.
 - Experimentation capacities (with data).

c) Kind of data to be shared by the members:

1. Results from agroecology best practices – including location (i.e., a map of the network).
2. Challenges encountered and potential solutions.
3. Existing policies to support agroecology practices.
4. Results from on-farm trials (sensors, remote sensing, soil, water quality, yield, crop physiology) - aggregated or not.
5. Others: Decision making process and outcome, indicators that will help following the agroecological transition, data on research (scientific data

on carbon assimilation in soils, yields and quality, biodiversity in soils and on the surface, emissions, and leaching, etc.)

d) Barriers to implement the Virtual Lab by the members

1. Standardization methods and data formats across the Member States; diversity of methods and assumptions in the data/results shared; diversity of situations, categories, quality of data.
2. Scientific data embargo before sharing.
3. Ability to engage actors other than the researchers.
4. Continuously encouraging actors to share their data and information.
5. Ensure complementarity/interoperability with other existing platforms.
6. GDPR.
7. Others: Data citation, need to demonstrate added-value/specific outputs, lack of common design/methodology leads to seemingly similar datasets not actually being equivalent, the need for metadata about how the data were collected to help their interpretation, some research infrastructures or living labs already have a platform like this one, lack of human capacity to upload large amount of data.

Figure 11. Mural results about the brainstorming on the Virtual Lab characteristics to fit the pilot network members' needs

2.2.4.5 Feedback on the experiences

After the first pilot network meeting, individual feedback calls were conducted with all 17 participants in January 2022 to gather the impressions and experiences of the members about the meeting. In addition, project partners also evaluated their experience about the workshops. The summary of general and workshop specific feedbacks can be found in **Appendix 9**.

2.2.4.6 Challenges

The challenges experienced during the three co-creation workshops are summarised in Table 6.

Co-creation workshop	Challenges
<i>Co-creation of joint collaborative activities</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It was difficult to translate and implement the mix of methods used during this workshop to an online format, which prevented obtaining detailed information on each member and to get to know each members' activities more in-depth. • The complexity of the workshop structure and methods was necessary to get the right information from the members, however it might have been difficult to understand and follow through for some. This resulted in some cases in the provision of inadequate or fragmented inputs by the members. • Finding ways to engage the members more interactively beyond the methods applied during these exercises.
<i>Exploring the competencies and skills for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The abstractness of the competencies and vagueness of the future network made it difficult for the members to understand right away and provide their expertise and inputs. It also created situations when the facilitators had to explain and clarify tasks more than expected. • The participation and input provided by project partners, who are not pilot network members, was confusing for the members and for the facilitators during this specific workshop, which might result in some biased outputs. • The combination of too many questions for the pilot network members without a clear action plan explaining for which action their input is needed is challenging.
<i>Building the Virtual Lab</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finding different tools and methods specific for LLs and RIs (and/or aligning them) that serve the better understanding and prototyping of the Virtual Lab. • Facilitation is better organised and remains balanced if working with more than one group. • Finding ways to engage the members more interactively beyond the mapping method applied during this workshop.

Table 6. Challenges of the three co-creation workshops

2.2.5 SWOT analysis of the co-creation methods used

Strengths
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methods used make possible the collection and validation of a wide range of information and inputs and the creation of new ideas from the different LLs/RIs. • Methods used fostered the better participation and inclusion of all members. • Learning from shared inputs and experiences from the members not only contributes to the overall goal of the ALL-Ready project, but it might inspire members to experiment with similar or new ideas and adopt different LL/RI practices. • The methods used give the members a sense of ownership and decision-making about the pilot network, capacity building program and the virtual lab tool. • The digital format of the methods makes the tasks, exercises, and participation measurable. • The digital format of the methods makes the workshop recordable and shareable therefore it can be revisited many times and evaluated more in-depth. • The results gained through the methods used help to design and build the next workshops and their methods. • Visual presentation of the inputs and ideas helped the better understanding and overview of the discussions and each workshop results for the members.
Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The methods used only make the gathering of inputs from the coordinators of LLs/RIs, but not from other stakeholders of each initiative, therefore the inputs collected can reflect one-sided experiences and opinions. • The use of some methods in an online format prevented to obtain detailed information from the members, often just ideas and half sentences via post-its, therefore they need to be revisited. • Online implementation of the methods lacks the in-person element which result in deeper discussions and better bonding between the members.
Opportunities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The members can bring in new ideas and ways for collaboration, knowledge-sharing, co-creation, and co-design and might contribute to shift from practice-based thinking to system thinking. • The feedbacks and debates received by the members will help them to evaluate their current LL/RI practices or ways of thinking and improve them. • The participation through the methods encourages networking among the peer members, which might lead to long-term cooperation. • The different methods and mixture of methods with the inclusion of fun elements help members to not only focus on practical, professional improvement but also to enjoy the co-creation process.
Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of willingness to be engaged through the methods due to time and capacity restraints or funding/resources. • Inadequate inclusion and involvement through the methods, and lack of proper input, data management and sharing among the members after the use of methods might lead to low participation during the next steps and mistrust. • Complexity of some methods might lead to confusion among the members which prevents them from contributing in a meaningful way. • Lack of inclusion of funny and new interactive elements during the methods might result in very dry co-creation experiences.

- Continuing the online use of the methods without any face-to-face interactions might lead to lower collaboration and co-creation potential, knowledge-sharing and quality input collection from the members.

3. Next steps

All the presented experiences will be considered to learn, progress further and plan the coming steps for each co-creation process and addressing the challenges encountered.

Joint network activities:

- A personal co-creation experience evaluation will be developed together with the pilot members to monitor and record all the experiences during the three co-creation processes (co-creating joint network activities, developing the Capacity Building Programme and building the Virtual Lab).
- Another co-creation workshop is foreseen in July to continue with the organization of collaborative activities, plan of action and network structure.
- Setting up the flow and frequency of the communication (e.g., emails) and the platform (online) for sharing knowledge, information (February onwards).
- Regular online meetings for the members will be introduced on trimonthly basis.

Capacity Building Programme:

- The Capacity Building Program will be developed further based on the inputs received.
- A prototype workshop will be organised for the members in July.

Virtual Lab:

- Another workshop is foreseen in parallel with the other two workshops to arrive to the defining features of the Agroecology Virtual Lab.

4. Conclusion

This document gave an overview about the recently established pilot network including its objectives, defining characteristics, activities and showcased its diversity through the presentation of all 15 members in detail situating them in the framework of agroecology transition.

The deliverable provided an in-depth analysis about the experiences and methods of the three co-creation workshops that took place during the first pilot network meeting. It is clear from the experiences that the involvement of all members in these processes facilitated learning from shared inputs and expertise that further inspired members to experiment with similar or new ideas, adopt different LL/RI practices or to assess their practices from a different perspective. The co-creation enhanced the sense of ownership and decision-making power of the members about the pilot network. It was widely acknowledged that the exercises done in the workshops supported networking and getting insight into the activities of peer members, which furthers long-term collaboration. On the other hand, the online format prevented the deeper discussion on specific common agroecological interests and the forming of personal connections between the members which had a negative effect on the experiences. Physical participation in upcoming pilot network meetings therefore will be essential.

For the organization of the next pilot network meetings and co-creation workshops, the challenges that emerged in this last meeting need to be considered. The use of complex methods should be avoided and rather application of short, but very simple tasks should be

prioritized. Moreover, a specific evaluation of the personal experiences of the members needs to be introduced that follows through the lifecycle of the pilot co-creation processes.

The experiences detailed in this document are preliminary as it contains the experiences from three separate workshops of one event, the first pilot network meeting. The experiences can only be understood and evaluated in frame of a two-year process within the ALL-Ready project. Therefore, this deliverable will be updated by new co-creation experiences in each year until the end of the project.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Presentation of the pilot network members

Institute for Sustainable Food (RI)

Context

The Institute for Sustainable Food at the University of Sheffield was launched in 2019 and encompasses three research pillars to address the whole food system: plant production and protection; translational and transformative research, and food consumption, health and sustainability. Research conducted within the institute brings together researchers from multiple disciplines to understand and transform whole-system food production from field to fork.

Aim: To address the challenges of food security and sustainability.

Activities

- Regenerative agriculture and soil health
- Land use policy and practice
- Improving biodiversity on agricultural land
- Protecting crop plants against pests and diseases
- Carbon sequestration potential of agricultural soils
- Better nitrogen use efficiency in crops, to reduce fertilizer inputs on field
- Increasing food production in urban areas

Sir David Read Controlled Environment Facility
Source: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/sdrcef>

Participants

Researchers, farmers, industry stakeholders, policy-makers

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The Institute for Sustainable Food seeks to discover new ways to understand the complexity within the food production system 'from farm to fork', addressing the agri-food system as a whole and not just in terms of its separate parts. Thus, integrating across the domains of production and consumption and embedding the needs of individual stakeholders from consumers and farmers to the wider business community, NGOs and government.

Diagrammatic representation of the agri-food ecosystem. Modified from Horton et al. (2017) Food Security 9: 195-210. Source: <https://www.sheffield.ac.uk/sustainable-food/about/vision>

Our approach recognises that achieving a sustainable food future is as much a socio-cultural problem as it is technological, understanding the global

nature of the food system while appreciating its impacts can be both local and global in scale.

Achievements

- Working with more than 100 different industry partners from across the farm to fork spectrum, including policymakers.
- 145 research groups are working to address challenges to food security and sustainability
- The Healthy Soil, Healthy Food, Healthy People (H3) project is a £6m consortium grant funded from the Transforming UK Food Systems call, which will transform the UK food system from the ground up.
- The Desert Garden Appeal is a unique project born out of innovative Sheffield science that is giving families displaced by war the opportunity to grow fresh food in the desert using the most unlikely of materials – discarded mattresses.

LifeWatch-ERIC (RI)

Context

LifeWatch-ERIC as an international organisation is adding knowledge and deepening understanding on biodiversity organisation and ecosystem functions and services in support of our societies to address the key planetary challenges.

Aim: To supply e-Science research facilities to the European scientific community to support decision-making processes.

Participants

Researchers, data providers, public administrators, policy-makers

Activities

- Offering new opportunities for large-scale scientific development,
- Supporting knowledge-based decision-making for biodiversity and ecosystem management,
- Providing training, dissemination and awareness programmes,
- FAIR data share, visualisation and models.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Using an innovative methodology, a modular Virtual Lab will be developed, to provide e-Services, either individually or in any type of possible combination (integration) in order to offer access, management and analyses to a wide range of data.

Such a Virtual Lab facilitates exploring all the information collected from end-to-end in each of the processes and practices (from the data collected by sensors to the socio-economic ones). It will foster agroecology transition, through a co-designed and co-developed tool to improve the problem-solving capacity of researchers, SMEs and entrepreneurs, and providing

evidence-based policy making capacities for government and funding bodies. Furthermore, citizen science activities are also planned.

CropSys (RI)

Context

Long-term experiment on organic and conventional arable cropping systems (CropSys) is running for 25 years and is based at the Department of Agroecology, Aarhus University (DK). It includes three experimental factors, has a factorial design, and is replicated in two blocks. The factors are cropping system (organic with grass-clover ley, organic with grain legume and conventional with grain legume), with and without cover crops, and with and without manure in the organic systems. Crops include cereals (barley, wheat, rye and oat) and grain legumes (faba bean, pea, lupin).

Aim: Exploring the possibilities for increasing soil fertility, productivity, and efficiency of arable cropping systems, by adopting different agroecological practices.

Activities

- Crop diversification in time and space:
 - Different crop sequences with inclusion of grain legumes and ley,
 - Cover crops,
 - Intercropping.
- Maintaining and improving soil health.
- Reducing negative environmental consequences of agriculture.
- Local production of plant-protein.

Participants

Researchers, farmers, advisors, technology providers

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

There is a close collaboration with farmer advisory services, companies (e.g., for development of machinery and tools) as well as with ICROFS (International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems). Together with these stakeholders, we organise several field days every year, with focus on different aspects. CropSys is used as a research platform by researchers and students with different expertise and scientific aims, allowing a comprehensive assessment of long- and short-term changes due to treatments and environmental factors.

Achievements

- Long-term data collected in a large database (which will be made more accessible).
- Established and new national and international collaborations.
- Funding ensured through continuous grant application efforts.

Centre for Circular Bioeconomy (RI)

Context

Aarhus University Centre for Circular Bioeconomy Production and Management of Agricultural Biomass (CBIO) is part of a research and development value chain for bioeconomy production systems and recirculation concepts, focusing on production of the raw material- biomass- for refining methods and on high-value products based on agricultural crops.

Principles & Values

CBIO supports scientifically the bio-based economy for replacing fossil raw materials with renewable plant-based materials, including for bioenergy production. Production and Management of Agricultural Biomass is the initial value within CBIO value-chain targeting refining of biomass.

***Aim:** Establishing and maintaining field trials for providing high-quality data from a plethora of agroecosystems, ranging from conventional grain crops to perennial herb crops and their combination, as well as data processing and results dissemination.*

Activities

- Establishment and management of field trials, including operations planning and management- sowing and re-sowing plants, fertilization and irrigation, pests and diseases management, equipment installation, data collection and compilation.
- Visualisation, quality-control and analysing all the data from the field trials.
- Sharing new knowledge with the world scientific community and sometimes with the general public.

Participants

Researchers, farmers, advisors, industry stakeholders

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

CBIO is working on creating high-quality field trial locations with representative agroecosystems for monitoring and measuring to kick-start a biobased economy with sustainable high-value products such as proteins, polymers, and new chemical or biological components for industry.

Illustration: Kiril Manevski

Achievements

- Important science achievements within CBIO agricultural biomass research infrastructure tackle the agronomic and the environmental characteristics of the agricultural biomass targeting future biorefineries:
- Design agroecosystems with prolonged coverage of the soil with biomass, thereby balancing biomass production and nitrogen leaching.
- Agroecosystems of perennial herbs produce large protein yields as promising and local alternative to the environmentally-costly overseas export of soy for animal feed.
- Finding lower nitrous oxide emissions from agroecosystems of perennial herbs compared to annual crops, despite their intensive field management.
- Land conversion from annual to perennial crops could be the win-win strategy for soil carbon and nitrogen sequestration.
- Effect of crop season on nitrogen leaching and of biomass-protein link related to plant life duration.

LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre (RI)

Context

LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre (ZAPVS) was established in 1994 in nouvelle Aquitaine, having a very large diversity of landscapes. Zone Atelier was created in 2009 forming a network together with LTSER and Recotox.

***Aim:** exploring solutions with stakeholders (farmers, citizens, beekeepers, etc.) to develop resilient agricultural socio-ecosystem practices.*

Participants

Local public bodies and municipalities, Researchers/Research institutes, Farmers, Consumers/Consumer organizations, NGOs

Activities

- Long term monitoring of biodiversity, ecological functions, land use and agricultural practices since 1994 for the oldest.

- Experiments at the landscape scale to understand the role of biodiversity in food production and farmers economic performance.
- Experimenting of nature-based and socioecological solutions, to foster agroecological solutions with farmers.
- Fostering the transformation of the agrifood system.
- Communication with local farmers and schools, national authorities and international community through publications.

REWET (RI)

Context

ReWet was established in 2021, in order to provide infrastructure at ecosystem scale to study the effect of rewetting drained agricultural and forest peatlands on greenhouse gas emissions (CO_2 , CH_4 and N_2O) and fluxes of nutrients (P and N), dissolved organic and inorganic carbon (DIC, DOC). In Denmark 10% of the GHG emissions is a result of drainage of peatlands, the national 70% GHG reduction goal by 2030 cannot be achieved without rewetting a substantial area of drained peatland. ReWet will establish four observatories on agricultural and forest peatland sites. These observatories will serve as platforms for ecosystem monitoring, experimental research, technological development, and demonstration.

***Aim:** to facilitate climate-smart management and land use change related to agriculture and forestry on soils with high organic carbon contents*

Participants

National, regional and local public bodies/authorities, researchers, advisors, farmers, processors, SMEs, NGOs

Activities

The research infrastructure aims to cover the variations in Danish peatlands. ReWet will establish observatories on four different sites.

- Gas flux measurements
- Emissions of GHG (CO_2 and CH_4) monitored in larger areas (>1 ha) at all sites by EC systems to represent the fluxes at ecosystem scale.
- Hydrology and water quality.
- Measure energy, nutrients, biodiversity changes.
- Guidelines for land-use policy and practice.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The ReWet observatories strengthen the links between the restoration of ecological and biogeochemical functions of peatlands and the wider benefits this can provide to society. Using the ReWet observatories as part of wider living laboratories on wetlands, the results generated contribute to solving the mosaic of challenges in wetland restoration, raising public awareness of the importance of peatlands for nature, the environment and climate, and finally, translating these into a language that is understood within broader policy forums.

Achievements

- Local authorities, farmers and researchers are co-creating an overall landscape strategy in which a multifunctional land consolidation scheme, whereby wetlands under agricultural use, are exchanged for agricultural land in less sensitive areas.
- Eight ha of agricultural peatland is used for sampling and analyses of drainage water, measurement of greenhouse gas emissions, paludiculture, and the testing of light machinery by Aarhus University.
- A commercial company delivers wet meadow grass to a research facility for biogas production and will be involved in future production of grass for biorefining.

OasYs system experiment (RI)

Context

OasYs is an agroecological dairy cattle system aiming to be adapted to climate change. Redesigned through a collaborative approach, it is carried out as a system experiment at the farm scale in an INRAE facility located in a French plain area already affected by summer droughts.

***Aim:** Enabling farmers to live from their dairy cattle system in a context of climate change, while saving water and fossil energy resources and contributing to sustainable agriculture*

Activities

- Forage diversification,
- Year-round grazing,
- Browsed fodder trees,
- Integrated livestock breeding strategies,
- Multicriteria assessment.

Participants:

Researchers, farmers, advisor, industry stakeholders

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

OasYs is an innovative system redesigned through a collaborative approach with various stakeholders. It relies on an agroecological approach, based on the diversity of the system's components and their functions, and aiming to adapt a low-input farm to climate change. It is experimented at the farm scale on an INRAE facility. The forage system (90 ha) produces the fodder necessary to feed the dairy cattle herd (72 milking cows, and replacement heifers) without irrigation and with limited use of mineral nitrogen fertiliser, whatever the climatic

hazards. The forage resources are diversified (including fodder trees) and priority is given to their grazing. The livestock breeding strategy is in coherence with the forage system, with two calving periods in spring and autumn, the extension of lactation length to 16 months and the three-way crossing of dairy breeds (Holstein, Scandinavian Red, Jersey). The system is evaluated in terms of its production performance, as well as its environmental and socioeconomic performance. It is a place for exchange with stakeholders.

Achievements

- The nutritive value of 31 tree, 14 shrub and 7 liana species has been assessed.
- Diversity of grazing resources enabled extension of grazing period.
- The increase of fat and protein contents offset the decrease in milk production.
- The system allowed 1.5 labour units to be remunerated at a rate equivalent to the income of two minimum wage earners.

ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab (LL)

Context

ÖMKi on-farm living lab is an agroecology-focused nationwide participatory experimentation network that includes a variety of field trials and technology tests co-designed and co-implemented with farmers with the aim to improve and/or develop new organic/agroecological practices, products, technologies.

***Aim:** Fostering scientific research on organic agriculture and contributing to agroecology transition in Hungary.*

Participants

Farmers, researchers, advisors, authorities, processors, retailers, consumers, and other industry stakeholders

Activities

Crop diversification for food system stability

- Ancient cereal variety tests and product development
- Landrace tomatoes - cultivation technologies
- Soybean in the crop rotation

Soil-building cultivation technologies

- Species-rich inter-row cover in vineyards and orchards
- Organic nutrient replenishment
- Herbicide-free tillage technologies (reduced-till, ground cover, etc.)

Precision farming solutions for organic agriculture

- Remote sensing for plant protection
- Sensors for developing customized feeding and disease prevention system

ÖMKi's on-farm network 2012-2018

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The Lab combines two processes into one complex system, that finally results in product/service/technology development. The so-called 'on-farm method' is an open innovation process in itself, that is used by the ÖMKi Lab to improve agricultural production practices in real-life farm settings (on the farm). The research involves farmers (or other end users) in all the steps, therefore they become active participants in the co-creation of the research from step 0. The real environment in every case is the actual farm of

the producer and the experiments are always adjusted to the farmers' production or environmental goals. As the Lab started to develop products, the on-farm method merged with the classical product development stages, thus creating its specific ÖMKi Lab product development process. In this process, the on-farm research is used to define and/or test agricultural product ideas and services and adjust them to a market gap. New product/service testing, development and improvement can also take place as a service of the Living Lab.

Achievements

- Yearly more than 100 farms take part voluntarily from the country.
- Introduction of organic bee health management against varroa mite.
- Variety tests and agrotechnical development in winter wheat, soya, potato and wine production.
- Number of technology and production guides for organic farming (tomato, grapevine, potato, fruit trees, soya bean etc.).
- Good information network among the stakeholders of each sector.
- Marketed products and services: Tomato landrace seedling package, Living interrow seed mixture, ancient emmer flour, organic advisory service.
- Opportunity to take part in EU research cooperation.

LLAEBIO - Living Lab Agroecology and Organic Agriculture (LL)

Context

The Living Lab Agroecology and Organic Agriculture (LLAEBIO), supports agroecological innovation as a lever in the transition to sustainable food and agricultural ecosystems in the region of Flanders (BE). This living lab brings together actors from the agri-food system with a shared interest in agroecology and organic farming to facilitate innovative research and to share knowledge and experiences. The overarching goal of LLAEBIO is to connect people, organizations, policy, science, and practice.

Principles & Values

From the beginning, LLAEBIO has used the basic ENOLL principles and components for living labs. These principles provide a steady compass for the members and their discussions and

practical activities. System thinking, the aim to join scientific and tacit knowledge, and strong stakeholder engagement and involvement are all seen as being indispensable to innovation.

***Aim:** Spread information, knowledge and expertise about agroecology and organic farming. Bring people together to facilitate mutual exchange of expertise and knowledge about agroecology and organic farming. Facilitate and support research and experiments on agroecology and organic farming.*

Participants

Researchers, farmers, advisors, industry stakeholders, teachers, policy makers

Activities

- Organization of interactive and educational knowledge-sharing activities in order to:
 - strengthen connection between stakeholders,
 - enhance farmers' knowledge about agroecological practices and opportunities (preferentially via peer-to-peer exchange),
 - raise all other actors' awareness of the potential of agroecology,
 - bring scientific knowledge to experiences on the field and vice versa.
- Identification of knowledge and research gaps within agroecology and organic farming;
- Support for and/or development of project proposals, in which agroecology and/or organic farming practices are investigated according to the 5 operational principles of living labs as defined by ENOLL (multi-method approach, multi-actor participation, real life context, involvement of end-users, co-creation and openness) and a transdisciplinary systems thinking approach;
- Deepening of our knowledge of systems research.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Annually, working themes are chosen together with key stakeholders of the living lab as part of an interactive workshop. Temporary participative working groups, formed of volunteers who participate based on their interests, are established to define and develop activities and actions on these themes. Depending on the specific goals of the working groups and the groups being targeted, the best tools and working methods (field visits, webinars, round tables, etc.) are explored and chosen. The activities target all actors in the agri-food system with an interest in agroecology and/or organic farming, e.g., farmers (conventional and organic/agroecological), farm suppliers and buyers, food processors, consumers, researchers in different disciplines, extension workers, (farm) advisors, teachers, policy makers, NGO members, and the like.

Defining themes of interest with LLAEBIO members during an annual interactive workshop

Achievements

Sharing knowledge and connecting people

- 'LLAEBIO draait door' is a quarterly event that keeps members up to date about LLAEBIO activities and provides a forum to partners to share their needs or experiences in projects or other activities (<https://www.llaebio.be/output>).
- Webinars on themes of interest. One such webinar was on 'fair pricing' in response to a farmer's question. An exploratory systems thinking exercise on that theme resulted in a series of 3 webinars with an exchange of theoretical and practical knowledge (<https://www.llaebio.be/output>).
- Webinar on sustainable soil management, with short videos of farmer testimonials (https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCkyum8O69TwK_xyHV8_Ls7A).
- Farm visits and demonstration days.
- An inspiration day for agricultural secondary school teachers to support teachers in introducing agroecology in education. We also contribute to courses on agroecology in higher education or post-school education.

Facilitation of innovative research

- Facilitation of the development of research projects by connecting (research) organizations or/and encouraging stakeholder engagement in projects.
- A shared PowerPoint presentation about the agroecology concept, with the aim of fostering understanding of the scientific foundations of agroecology. We also support the creation of a science-based agroecology think tank.
- Round table discussions to define research priorities together with the organic sector.

Occitanum (LL)

Context

Occitanum is an archipelago of 13 Living Labs deployed on different pedo-climatic and production sites across the Occitanie Region. These user-centred labs bring together all the local and regional stakeholders to develop innovative projects for a variety of agricultural and local food systems. Occitanum follows an original structure allowing flexibility and complementarity. It is based on seven open labs based on six production systems (beekeeping, orchards, vineyard, field crops, livestock, market gardening) and one on local supply chain. Each open lab is dispatched on different pilot sites, each with a different innovative project with its specific governance. General governance is managed through the core entity allowing for the general coordination, research and training actions, valorisation, and financial actions.

***Aim:** Deploying digital technologies to foster agroecology transition and regionalise food supply.*

Participants

Farmer communities, local authorities, agricultural development actors, AgTech firms, citizens as well as researchers, engineers, technicians, and academics.

Activities

- Establish and implement innovative projects:
 - test new digital solutions in a real-world environment
 - develop co-innovation with stakeholders
- Codevelop innovative methods,

- Foster involvement of AgTech Firms in open innovation processes,
- Develop multi-disciplinary research,
- Assessment of the potential of digital technologies used in Open Labs.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Different tools are used to get a good stakeholder participation and involvement:

- Regular meetings even during the Covid crises using participatory remote tools.
- Transparent and clear method called "service map" that allow to go from the stakeholder's need to the requirement for AgTech to develop new products.
- Call for interest to the AgTech enterprise to propose solutions to farmers.
- Development of robust protocols to evaluate innovative solution in real life.
- Training on AgTech to motivate the different stakeholders.

Achievements

- 49 partners involved,
- 25 emerging innovative projects,
- 7 working group to co-build (data, research, ideal open lab, training, assessment).

PA4ALL (LL)

Context

PA4ALL is an abbreviation for Precision Agriculture for All, which is the main scope of our Living Lab, to introduce all the actors in the agriculture production chain to precision agriculture tools. The host organization of PA4ALL is BioSense Institute, Institute for research and development of information technology in biosystems. Research and innovation at BioSense Institute is developed in a close interaction with farmers and the agri-food sector, government bodies, entrepreneurs and business community, international researchers, and citizens.

***Aim:** To create a meeting place for all relevant stakeholders and a new generation of open innovations which will be readily used, and which will bring benefits across the entire value-chain.*

Activities

- Introducing precision agriculture to high school students.
- Installing meteorology stations around Serbia to enhance the adaption of precision agriculture.
- Creating a free online service which involves precision agriculture tools.

Participants

Researchers, farmers, citizens, students, industry stakeholders, policy makers.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

Since BIOS Institute (PA4ALL) is involved in multidisciplinary research performed in the fields of micro and nanoelectronics, communications, signal processing, remote sensing, big data, robotics and biosystems we include academia and highly skilled professionals to share their knowledge on the subject.

We engage policy makers and representatives of the governmental and civil society in conversation about the importance of equipping the society with precision agriculture tools and the following knowledge. We have a broad system of stakeholders in Serbia, such as teachers, professors, students, citizens, agriculture producers, SMEs, non-governmental organizations, and others who we involve in our activities and projects.

Innovative Farmers (LL)

Context

Innovative Farmers is a non-profit network that gives farmers in the UK research support and funding on their terms. This helps farmers find lasting solutions to practical problems, from managing weeds and pests with fewer chemicals to testing more sustainable animal feeds. Members of the network can connect with other innovative farmers, researchers and stakeholders who share a passion for finding new ways to farm and can take part in farmer-led trials, known as “field labs”. The programme covers all farming sectors and works with both conventional, regenerative, and organic farmers.

***Aim:** To speed up the adoption of innovative practices that increase farm sustainability, resilience and animal health and welfare as well as enhancing farmers' confidence in on-farm experimentation and fostering new collaborations.*

Activities

- Specialist advice and support to get field labs off the ground.
- Connecting farmers with other farmers and facilitating the co-design process, and with researchers for advice on trial design and time to do assessments, monitoring, and analysis.
- Matching the group with a coordinator to keep the field lab on track and facilitating the co-design process, as well as a researcher for advice on trial design and time to do assessments, monitoring, and analysis.
- Organising network events, conference sessions and other field lab open days.

Soil scientists Lynda Deeks trains hemp growers on low-cost ways to assess their soil health in a field lab exploring how growing hemp impacts soil health, carbon sequestration and biodiversity.

- Communication: open days, webinars, monthly e-newsletters, knowledge exchange videos and blogs, social media, open-source publishing of progress and findings, dedicated web content for each field lab, and working with the farming media to feature field labs and the farmers in the network.
- Reporting, evaluation, and quality assurance. This includes input from a steering group made up of industry experts and academics who assess field lab applications.

Participants

Farmers, researchers, advisors, NGOs, industry stakeholders.

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

How to set up a field lab

1 It starts with an idea

From an existing discussion group, project or network, a group of farmers or growers come together around an idea

2 Identifying existing knowledge and a suitable topic

Supported by a coordinator, the group establishes a topic or challenge they'd like to explore and sets realistic expectations and outcomes for the field lab.

3 Formulating a clear research question and co-designing a trial

Innovative Farmers matches the group with a researcher so they can develop a practical research question to be answered through a field lab. The group works collaboratively to design what data to record and monitor, ensuring the trial is both scientifically robust and practical for a working farm. The plan should be realistic about the roles, responsibilities, and time that the trialists and researchers can commit

4 Applying for funding

The group can apply to the Innovative Farmers Research Fund to cover trial costs.

5 Progressing the field lab

The group meets regularly and uses social media to discuss insights and tips and make sure the trial stays on track and data is collected regularly.

6 Analyse results

The group jointly analyses the findings and identifies what they have discovered over the duration of the field lab.

7 Share findings

The results and tips are shared with the farming community through events, online and in the media so everyone can benefit.

8 Next steps

The farmers apply what they have learned to their farming business and explore whether a new field lab or other funding streams are needed to answer further questions.

Achievements

- Launched over 120 field labs across the UK.
- Over 600 farmers have taken part in on-farm trials through the field labs.
- Half of farmers have made changes to their farming practices because of field labs.
- Real changes on the ground include:
 - 50% of UK hops growers now grow cover crops in their hop yards.
 - Identifying innovative solutions which increase farm sustainability and reduce costs.
 - Supporting large, long-term, participatory trials, looking at silvopasture.
 - Changes on individual farms, e.g., growing buckwheat as a permanent part of a rotation for couch grass control.
- Farmers and researchers equipped with research evidence to make the case for further government support for agroecological practices.
- Farmers and researchers demonstrating the value of collaboration and on-farm trials, enabling them to access larger external funding pots to continue with their research.
- 84% of people in the network have learned something new.
- 12,000 farmers have engaged in another activity such as attending on-farm events, conferences, watching our knowledge exchange videos or reading the Innovative Farmers newsletter.

- Showcasing the network: Farming press coverage of field lab activity and farmer voices is read over 133,000 times a month.

CARBONFARM (LL)

Context

Carbonfarm is a cooperation between the Danish agricultural universities at Aarhus and Copenhagen, The Danish Innovation Centre for Organic farming, Danish low-till farmer association (FRDK), four skilled and innovative farmers and the Danish Agro-industry. Carbonfarm combines research and a practical approach to develop and demonstrate sustainable agricultural systems for the future.

***Aim:** By bringing together the researchers, advisors, and innovative farmers the aim of Carbonfarm is to develop, document and implement sustainable farming systems based on conservation agriculture principals in both organic and conventional farming.*

Participants

Researchers, NGOs, farmers, and advisors.

Activities

- Research in agronomic, climate and environmental effects of conservation agricultural (CA) systems: (soil structure, weeds, yields and quality, nitrous oxide emissions; nutrient assimilation - and leaching, etc.
- Measure and document effects of CA systems on biodiversity (bees, beetles, earthworms, soil surface predators, antipodes (collembola), arbuscular mycorrhiza, etc.
- Research effects and mechanisms of CA for building up the soil carbon content (measuring and modelling carbon content in soils).
- Develop and implement a sustainable system with Conservation Agriculture elements suitable for Danish conventional and organic farming systems.
- Develop mechanical solutions for Danish CA primarily in organic trials.
- Demonstration and dissemination of project results to farmers, researchers and advisory services (field days, seminars, webinars, visit from local and international farmers/experts, manuals, videos and articles etc.).

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The Carbonfarm living lab is based on established large scale field trials at four Danish farms. Two conventional and two organic farms are involved. The treatments are a reference of a traditional plough system, a low tillage system without ploughing, and two conservation agricultural systems with low- or no till systems. Field Plots are 20 – 24 x 50 meters and the trials are run by/with farmers using their own machinery – with a few exceptions.

Living lab field trials:

- Treatment 1: Reference (Normal tillage intensity with ploughing). Limited use of catch crops.
- Treatment 2: "Low tillage". Without ploughing mainly cultivation by harrowing and use of catch crops.
- Treatment 3: CA "Minimal tillage, " leaving plant residues and optimal use of catch crop in mixtures.
- Treatment 4: CA "Carbon optimising", with minimal tillage.

Achievements

- CA is also a robust and sustainable cultivation system under Danish conditions.
- The non-organic experimental fields show that CA can be implemented, and yields can be obtained similar to traditional cultivation systems with tillage.
- There is great interest among conventional farmers to operate their plant-breeding in whole or in part according to CA principles.
- Weed control is a major challenge when plowing and tillage are reduced in organic crops.
- CA has a significant potential to increase biodiversity both above and below ground in Danish fields, although the positive effects on aphid predators only affected the spiders.

ROADMAP (LL-like project)

Context

ROADMAP is a 4-year EU-funded project that will foster transitions towards prudent antimicrobial use (AMU) in animal production in a large variety of contexts, by favouring a rethinking of antimicrobial decision-systems all along the food supply chain.

Aim: foster transitions towards prudent use of antimicrobials (AMs) in animal production in different contexts to manage antimicrobial resistance (AMR). Reduced antimicrobial use (AMU) will be achieved by enhancing antimicrobial decision-systems along the food and drug supply chains. ROADMAP will focus on supporting animal health and welfare through prevention and health promotion actions.

Participants

National public bodies/authorities, local public bodies and municipalities, researchers/research institutes, universities, advisors, farmers, retailers, SMEs, large companies, and consumers/consumer organizations.

Activities

- analyse the socio-economic drivers of AMU,
- engage with animal health professionals, stakeholders, and policy makers.
- develop tailored strategies for change and propose transition scenarios in diverse farm animal production systems in Europe and low- and middle-income countries.

Organic Research, Development, and Demonstration Program (Funding scheme)

Context

ICROFS, International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems, founded in 1996, hosts the Organic RDD program with projects supporting the Danish organic farming and food systems, funded by the Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries. Organic RDD is providing funds for LLs and RIs. Supported projects must include a research part and the results be focused on the end-user through multi-actor approach organised LL.

Principles & Values

ICROFS is contributing to the development of sustainable food systems based on the organic philosophy and the organic principles. It contributes with new knowledge, which supports reliability, innovation and development of organic farming and food systems.

***Aim:** The development of a market-driven and competitive organic sector and the support of continuous growth in the Danish organic sector.*

Participants

Funders, ministry, researcher, farmers, NGOs, and industry stakeholders.

Activities

- Coordinating the Organic RDD program
- Coordinating the European ERA-NET Core Organic
- Participate as partners in research projects: communication, dissemination, and knowledge synthesis. Project management
- Runs the open access archive Organic Eprints (including Germany and Switzerland)
- Produces knowledge synthesis about organic farming

Methods, stakeholder engagement and tools

The Organic RDD program focuses on actor driven research by use of multi-actor approach organic LL.

The funded projects must include end-users and must include actors from the whole value chain from the planning phase.

Achievements

- ICROFS has coordinated Danish Organic research calls since 1996.
- ICROFS has coordinated the ERA-NET Core Organic since 2004 and has coordinated 6 transnational calls.
- Produces knowledge synthesis about organic farming.

Appendix 2: Meeting agenda

DAY 1

13 December Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
9:55 -10:00	Waiting for everyone to join via zoom	
10:00 – 10:30	Introductory round (ice-breakers)	All
10:30 – 10:45	Introduction to the meeting’s objectives, facilitators and to the Pilot Network	Korinna Varga, ÖMKi
10:45 – 10:55	ALL-READY project	Heather McKhann, INRAE
10:55 – 11:15	European Agroecology Partnership	Benjamin Sanchez, SCAR-AE
11:15 – 11:20	Break	
11:20 - 12:20	ALL-READY: Mission and Vision of the future European Agroecology Network	Muriel Mambrini, Bastian Goldel, INRAE
12:20 – 13:20	Lunch break	
13:20 – 14:20	Pilot member (LLs/RIs) introduction PART 1 1. LLAEBIO (Living Lab on Agro-Ecology and Organic Farming in Flanders) 2. PA4ALL 3. Long term experiment on organic and conventional arable cropping systems (CROPSYS) 4. Carbon Farm 5. Occitanum 6. OasYs	Pilot members
14:20 – 14:30	Yoga Break	

14:30 – 15:30	Pilot member (LLs/RIIs) introduction PART 2 7. ÖMKi On-Farm Living Lab 8. Innovative Farmers 9. ROADMAP 10. LifeWatch ERIC 11. LTSER Zone Atelier Plaine & Val de Sèvre 12. ReWet_DK	Pilot members
15:30 – 15:40	Yoga Break	
15:40 – 16:30	Pilot member (LLs/RIIs) introduction PART 3 13. Agricultural Climate Solutions 14. Organic Research Development and Demonstration Program 15. Institute for Sustainable Food 16. BIOBASE (CBIO) 17. Guadalinfo Living Lab	
16:30– 17:00	Pilot network expectations exercise	Korinna Varga, Judit Fehér, ÖMKi
17:00– 17:10	Conclusion, End of 1st Day	Korinna Varga, ÖMKi
17:10-17:45	Grab a drink and imagine the future of your LL/RI (Virtual Networking)	Everyone

DAY 2

14 December Time	Activity	Presenters, Facilitators
9:25 – 9:30	Waiting for everyone to join via zoom	
9:30 – 10:20	<u>Engaging with the WPs</u> WP presentations, timeline of related activities Discussion round with the participants	WP Leads
10:20 – 12:00	Co-creation of joint activities for the pilot network (workshop)	Korinna Varga, Judit Fehér, ÖMKi
12:00 - 13:00	Lunch break	
13:00 – 15:00	Exploring the added value of a future network and competencies for transition to agroecology and to run LL/RI (workshop)	Gerald Schwartz (TI), Isidora Stojacic (Biosense), Jo Bijtbeier (ILVO), Sylvie Fosselle (ILVO), Marion Liberloo (ILVO) Koen Vervoort (ENoLL)
15:00 – 15:10	Break	
15:10 – 16:50	Building a Virtual Lab that suits the pilot network members' needs (workshop)	José Manuel Avila, Juan Miguel Gonzalez Aranda, Life Watch ERIC
16:50– 17:10	Conclusion & next steps End of the 1st pilot meeting	Korinna Varga, ÖMKi

Appendix 3: List of participants

Nr	Name	Organization/affiliation	Type of stakeholder
1	Anton Rasmussen	CarbonFarm	LL coordinator/Organic advisor
2	Bastian Goldel	INRAE	WP1 Lead/Note-taker
3	Benjamin Sanchez	SCAR-AE	Presenter
4	Chiara de Notaris	CROPSYS	RI coordinator/Researcher
5	Chris McPhee	AAFC	LL coordinator/ Innovation management specialist
6	Gerald Schwartz	TI	WP4 Lead/Expert
7	Gerardo Romero	Guadalinfo	LL coordinator/Network coordinator
8	Heather McKhann	INRAE	Project Coordinator
9	Holly Croft	Institute for Sustainable Food	RI coordinator/Researcher
10	Isidora Stojacic	PA4ALL	LL coordinator/WP4 expert
11	Ivana Trkulja	Organic RDD	Scientific officer
12	Jacques-Eric Bergez	Occitanum	LL coordinator/ Researcher
13	Jo Bijttebier	ILVO	WP5 facilitator
14	Jose Manuel Avila	LifeWatch-ERIC	RI coordinator/WP6 Lead/Facilitator
15	Juan Miguel Gonzalez Aranda	LifeWatch ERIC	WP6 Lead/Facilitator
16	Judit Fehér	ÖMKi	WP3 Lead/Facilitator
17	Kiril Manevski	CBIO	RI coordinator/Researcher
18	Koen Vervoort	ENoLL	WP5 Lead/Note-taker
19	Korinna Varga	ÖMKi On-farm Living Lab/ÖMKi	LL coordinator/WP3 Lead/Facilitator
20	Lieve de Cock	LLAEBIO	LL coordinator /Researcher
21	Malene Jakobsen	Organic RDD	RI coordinator/Scientific officer
22	Merete Studnitz	ROADMAP	LL coordinator/ Scientific officer
23	Muriel Mambrini	INRAE	WP1 Lead/Facilitator
24	Ophélie Bonnet	INRAE	Project Manager
25	Paola Eulalio	DG Agri	Policy maker
26	Rebecca Swinn	Innovative Farmers	LL coordinator/Network coordinator
27	Rocio Mantero Cejudo	LifeWatch ERIC	WP6 Facilitation

28	Sabrina Gaba	ZAPVS	RI coordinator/Researcher
29	Sandra Novak	OasYs	RI coordinator/Researcher
30	Susana Gaona-Saez	DG Agri	Policy maker
31	Sylvie Fosselle	ILVO	WP5 facilitator
32	Torsten Berg	REWET	LL coordinator/ Researcher
33	Vincent Bretagnolle	ZAPVS	Researcher

Appendix 4: Individual challenges of members

Affected Member	Individual Challenges
Occitanum (LL)	Develop full innovative digital tools assessment (LCA, SLCA, EA)
	Deal with the differences in the different Open Labs
LLAEBIO (LL)	Tightening the link between organic and conventional sector
	Setting up (and fund) new research activities
Innovative Farmers (LL)	Getting 5 agricultural colleges to include farmer-led research/on-farm trials as part of modules
	Continuation of some field labs (facilitation, research requirements of farmers)
	Structuring better the LL - e.g., value of steering group, delivery to partners
CROPSYS (RI)	Keeping long-term coherence while addressing new needs
CarbonFarm (LL)	Implementing conservation agricultural practices in organic farming
Organic RDD	How to coordinate with other research programs of similar kind
PA4ALL (LL)	How to keep confidentiality, but at the same time, disseminate LL outcomes
LifeWatch (RI)	Designing tools for LLs and RIs and the collection of enough data to validate and test them

Appendix 5: Five collaborative themes detailing specific activities with potential collaborators

Collaborative Theme 1	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments (comparable between different contexts)	Test, document and improve the agronomic, climate and environmental effects of conservation agriculture	Occitanum, IF, ISF, ÖMKi, CROPSYS, Carbonfarm, ZAPVS, AAFC, LLAEBIO, LifeWatch
	Test new digital solutions to help the transition to agroecology, e.g., remote sensing for plant protection, reducing tomato crop losses with plant sensors	Occitanum, LifeWatch, PA4ALL, Guadalinfo, ISF, ÖMKi, AAFC, Carbonfarm, Cropsys, IF
	Carbon sequestration, GHG emission, improving soil (cover crops, hemp cultivation) and water conservation to mitigate climate change (e.g., trials on no-till, reduced-till with living mulches)	ISF, ZAPVS, Carbonfarm, LLAEBIO, AAFC, IF, LifeWatch, ÖMKi, OasYs
	Diversification (crop, production, rotational) on multiple level e.g., intercropping exploring good combinations and yields, soybean variety tests for crop rotation	OASYS, CROPSYS, ZAPVS, ISF, IF, ÖMKI, Carbonfarm, LLAEBIO, AAFC
	Organic nutrient replenishment	ÖMKi, IF, AAFC, CROPSYS
	Improving the targeting of mastitis treatments to reduce antibiotic use, improve animal welfare, develop decision system	ROADMAP, IF
	Silvopasture (integrating trees with livestock) impact on livestock health, soils, and biodiversity	IF, OASYS
	Drought resilient forage	IF, OASYS
	Testing the role of biodiversity in biocontrol,	Carbonfarm, ZAPVS, ISF

	pollination, organic matter recycling	
Cross-cutting activities:	Conducting fixed (yield, nitrate leaching, weed pressure, nutrients) and extra measurements on the side (biological N ₂ fixation, N ₂ O emissions, vegetation indices, better nitrogen use efficiency) in all the above topics	ISF, AAFC, CROPSYS, ÖMKi
	Multi-criteria assessment at the farm level and valorisation of different dimensions (crop rotation, cow lifetime) in the above topics	LifeWatch, OASYS, Occitanum
	Scientific data analysis, management, and storage in the above topics	ROADMAP, CROPSYS, LifeWatch, ÖMKi (only in analysis)

Collaboration Theme 2	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing	Communication, promotion of members' agroecology-related research, project results and knowledge e.g., via website, learning networks, social media, webinar series	Organic RDD, CarbonFarm, IF, ÖMKi, AAFC, LifeWatch, CROPSYS, LLAEBIO, PA4ALL, ROADMAP, ZAPVS
	Knowledge-sharing on AE and specifically on LL approach	ÖMKi, AAFC, ROADMAP, LifeWatch, RDD, Occitanum
	Capacity-building/training/awareness on LL methods, on how to involve non-academic actors as partners for innovation (stakeholder network development)	AAFC, IF, Guadalinfo, Organic RRD, LLAEBIO, ZAPVS, Carbonfarm, PA4ALL, ÖMKi
	Determination of knowledge gaps in relation to member agroecology LLs/RIs activities and for AE transition	LLAEBIO, ROADMAP, ÖMKI
	Pilot educational model for precision agriculture solutions in agroecology, introduce tools to high school, improve digital literacy	Guadalinfo, PA4ALL, Occitanum

Collaboration Theme 3	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Collaboration in long-term monitoring of agroecosystems	Monitoring of biodiversity, ecological functions, and land use	ZAPVS, LLAEBIO, CROPSYS, AAFC, ROADMAP

Collaboration Theme 4	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Advice for evidence-based agricultural policy development	Policy recommendations to support knowledge-based decision making for biodiversity, agroecosystem management	ROADMAP, ZAPVS, Guadalinfo, LifeWatch, ÖMKi
	Ex-ante impact assessments	LifeWatch

Collaboration Theme 5	Specific Activity	Potential Collaborators
Facilitation of EU project proposal development	Linked to the agroecological topics mentioned in Collaborative Theme 1	LLAEBIO, Organic RDD, BIOBASE, ROADMAP

Appendix 6: Future activities with potential collaborators

Future activities/agroecological research topics	Link to Collaborative Theme/Joint Network Activity	Potential Collaborators
Monitoring impact of agroecology: data collection to assess economic impact of agroecology	Measuring, evaluating the impact of the pilot members' activities, research	LLAEBIO, ÖMKi
Research on organic mixed farming	Collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments	Organic RDD, ÖMKi
Research on agroforestry	Collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments	Organic RDD, CarbonFarm, IF, LLAEBIO
Test of soybean (harvested fresh for food) in crop rotation (weed suppression, pest and disease chain, nutrient use efficiency)	Collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments	CROPSYS, IF

Best practice for growing culturally appropriate crops + routes to market	Collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments	IF, ÖMKi
Controlling wireworm in potatoes – management	Collaborative research to test specific agroecological practices with farmers through field trials/experiments	IF, AAFC, ÖMKi
Co-creation of activities/research with more diversified stakeholders (e.g., co-design of new tools for AE transition (cropping design))	Collaboration for knowledge exchange and information sharing	CROPSYS, AAFC, ÖMKi, ROADMAP, PA4ALL, LifeWatch
Applying for project proposals	Facilitation of EU project proposal development	ROADMAP, Organic RDD, ÖMKi

Appendix 7: Pilot member specific competencies

Occitanum is working on a tool and different indicators regarding the use of digital technologies. So, they have expertise in modelling and multicriteria and multi-actor assessment and practical experience.

ÖMKi has expertise in on-farm methodologies, networking, documented methods, and the ability to teach (for newcomers) and share them. They also have experience in multi-actor product development, e.g., knowledge about how to develop products with a variety of actors of the food chain (workshop).

PA4ALL has expertise in ecosystem building, understanding of main issues to address, capability to assign right people to be part of the problem solving and a wide network and are integrated in different organisations.

Innovative Farmers has expertise around networking (but no guide) and in forming farmer groups and facilitating conversation. However, they very often use external advisors from the Soil Association who launched the Innovative Farmers programme.

LLAEBIO has experience with systems thinking.

OasYs has expertise in systemic approach for mixed crop-dairy system.

LifeWatch is strong in co-creation of digital tools for data/knowledge management, a community of stakeholders working on agroecology and linking biodiversity with environmental processes.

CropSys has expertise in policy requirements and national framework, collaboration with industrial partners and farm advisors but not so much with other stakeholders and scientific communication.

ZAPVS is well experienced in biodiversity monitoring and biodiversity and ecosystem functioning.

AAFC is working as a network of living labs to share results, data, intellectual property etc. They have experience in modelling/satellite imagery, competencies among biophysical scientists, in surveys/analysis, evaluation of living labs (e.g., research agenda, scoping review, building useful indicators for managing living labs and for convincing funders).

Appendix 8: Role of the Future Network

1. Developing skills for facilitation and organisation of co-creation sessions, both at the design level of co-creation and at the level of basic facilitation of events.

2. Developing skills and knowledge on how to set up a LL/RI:

This knowledge and skills can be developed by offering:

- A platform to share best practices, e.g., showcasing best practices to motivate actors/raise awareness. Participants indicated that mainly consumers and other value chain actors are the targets that they are struggling to connect with. It might be relevant to showcase best practices in case studies that do connect and engage with these kind of actors (exchanging best practices and learning from mistakes)
- Training sessions and workshop
- A library of best practices (taking context into account)
- 1–2-page guides
- Simple videos instead of complicated documents
- Space for organising distributed experiments based on key drivers of change. Individual LL/RI could experiment with these key drivers to test them by doing socio-ecological experiments. Data can be shared by Virtual Lab. Key drivers and challenges might be the themes that can be covered with the thematic working groups within the network.

Participants noted that, in Europe, many different cultural contexts exist, which might also have an impact on engaging farmers and facing the challenges. Even more, in different countries, there is a different organization of innovation and knowledge systems, so different methodologies or strategies may be needed to bring together different stakeholders. Furthermore, different Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) exists in different countries. So, strategies to bring stakeholders together might also be different between countries/regions. Therefore, guidance with specific practices might be useful that takes these cultural differences into account. The problem that countries have in setting up LL are probably shared, but the way to deal with them or solutions might depend on the context. The network should provide general building blocks for capacity building (participatory, agroecology, social...) which can be specified in local contexts because education and training are culturally defined, languages are different and farmers and some actors of the agri-food value chain (advisors...) do not always understand English. However, participants mentioned that the national level will remain crucial to organise capacity building, even when a European network is created, but in some countries, they do not want to spend funds on organising capacity building.

Other benefits of a European network might be:

- Information exchange at the European level,
- Development of a suitable funding strategy,
- Increasing robustness of evidence and potential for awareness raising of opportunities and benefits of transitions for farmers, consumers, and other actors in the value chain,
- Increasing impact and outreach – Potential for a European network to become a key driver of change,
- Organisation of events.

Appendix 9: Feedback on the experiences

General feedback on the online format and MURAL:

- The tasks were more straightforward and easier to follow for those who are more computer-savvy and used to online workshops, but others with lack of experience couldn't contribute as much.
- Makes the work more convenient and quicker to work with predefined information (agroecological interests, needs and expectations) which mainly requires approval/disapproval and less thinking from the members.
- Face-to-face contacts were missing, which would have helped more detailed and deeper understanding of members' thoughts and (mis)understandings and necessary intervention of facilitators.
- Although the work and interactions in small groups were very useful, members signalled that they would have talked more during a physical meeting, compared to the online format.

Joint activities

Online format, MURAL:

- Useful visual representation of results, inputs gathered before which helped the members' understanding on expectations and needs of the pilot network.

Methods:

- The three methods applied were interesting, useful, interactive, and served the purpose of the workshop, though the timeframe was too short and would have been way more productive physically.
- Many members saw collaboration potential right away during match-making due to the number of different types of information visually provided on each initiative (not just hearing it in the presentations) which got them curious.
- The challenges part was difficult to fill in for some (less time and complex answers were required).
- A few signalled that it was difficult to understand what other initiatives are aiming to do and how we will work further by collaborating with one another as it was new and hard to comprehend and process this much information presented at once.
- The follow-up of this exercise would be important, especially in case of project and non-project partners teaming up to bridge the gaps.

Capacity building and competencies

Online format, MURAL:

- Music was played during some individual exercises which did not help the thinking of the members, however for a few it was soothing.

Methods:

- The overall workshop was well-structured but some felt it was a bit abstract compared to other workshops in the pilot meeting.
- Tasks were a bit difficult to do, felt vaguer and different, members often got lost and confused, not really getting the point on the different level of experiences.
- The tasks were not self-explanatory.
- The rowing example before the exercise that explained the objective of the workshop in advance was really creative and was a good warm-up.

Building the Virtual Lab

Online format, MURAL:

- Although the work and interactions in small groups were very useful, discussion only occurred in one of the groups. In the other group, members filled in the Mural quietly

and discussion was not initiated by the facilitator which created a strange, impersonal environment.

Methods:

- The workshop was concrete, well-built, with visual tools used that served well the mapping tasks.
- There was a perceptible difference between LLs and RIs in understanding the importance of the Virtual Lab and the related tasks. Mainly RIs expressed that they are very much interested in Virtual Lab and could use it in the future, but still need some work or further workshops to better understand it.
- However, for some, mainly LLs, the exercise and used method was not entirely understandable and they could not make the relation with their LL activities.